

C₁₈H₂₇N₃O₃ is capsaicin. It makes stuff spicy. Find a way to remove the nitrogen atom from it, then add C₁₀H₉O₁₂. It makes neohesperidin dihydrochalcone, which is sweet. This is just theoretical. (I'm only a kid, I have no idea about this stuff)

NO PLAGIARISM INTENDED